

Asset market experiment

Instruction

This experiment is an experiment on decision-making regarding market transactions. The amount of earnings you receive is determined by the decisions of you and other participants, and random factors. Please make sure you understand the instruction of this experiment and make the appropriate decisions. The payment for this experiment will be paid in cash after the end of this experiment.

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I The flow of the entire experiment (1)

In this experiment:

- **fourteen participants in one.** Seven participants are **Type-A**, seven participants are **Type-B**.
- The type for each participant is assigned randomly and remain unchanged until the end of the experiment.
- You trade virtual shares with other participants in a group using the experimental currency (cents).
- The group members **remain the same until the end of the experiment**.
- We call one experiment one **Round**, which consists of **10 periods**.

Section 1. The flow of the entire experiment.

In this experiment, participants are divided into groups of fourteen.

In each group, 7 participants are Type-A, and the remaining 7 participants are Type-B.

Your type is assigned randomly by the computer and remains unchanged until the end of the experiment.

You trade virtual shares with other participants in a group using the experimental currency.

In this experiment, the experimental currency is denoted as “cents”.

The members of the other thirteen participants are the same until the end of the experiment.

In the following, we call one experiment one round.

One round consists of 10 periods.

I The flow of the entire experiment (2)

At the beginning of each round:

- **1200 cents** of experimental currency

- Each **Type-A** participant holds **6 units** of A-shares
- Each **Type-B** participant holds **3 units** of B-shares
 - The shares pay dividends in experimental currency at the end of each period. (more details will be introduced in Section II later.)

At the beginning of each round, you will receive 1,200 cents in experimental currency.

Additionally, if you are Type-A, you will receive 6 units of A-shares; if you are Type-B, you will receive 3 units of B-shares.

The shares pay dividends in experimental currency at the end of each period. More details on the shares and dividends will be introduced later in Section II.

I The flow of the entire experiment (3)

- In each period, you can buy shares using cents, or sell shares and receive cents from other participants within the same group. (This will be introduced in Section III later.)
- At the end of each period, the cents and shares you hold will be carried over to the next period.
 - However, **after the 10th period, all shares will lose their value and vanish.**
- Your **payment will be calculated based on the balance of cents remaining after the 10th period.** (More detail will be introduced in Section V later.)

In each period, you can purchase shares using cents, or sell shares and receive cents from other participants within the same group. More details on how to trade shares will be introduced later in Section III.

At the end of each period, the cents and shares you hold will be carried over to the next period.

However, after the 10th period, all shares will lose their value and vanish.

Your payment will be calculated based on the balance of cents remaining after the 10th period.

More details on how to calculate the payment will be introduced later in Section V.

I I Shares and dividends (1)

- In this experiment, there are two types of shares: **A-shares** and **B-shares**.
- During each period, all participants, including you, can trade both types of shares.
- At the end of each period, you will receive dividends from the shares you hold.
- The amount of the dividends depends on the type of shares.

Section 2. Shares and dividends

In this experiment, there are two types of shares: A-shares and B-shares.

During each period, all participants, including you, can trade both types of shares.

Consequently, participants classified as Type-A can trade both A-shares and B-shares. Similarly those classified as Type-B can trade both A-shares and B-shares.

At the end of each period, you will receive dividends from the shares you hold.

The amount of the dividends depends on the type of shares.

II Shares and dividends (2)

At the end of each period, the dividend amount for each unit of **A-shares** and **B-shares** is determined as follows:

- The dividend for each **A-share** is randomly drawn from 0, 8, 28, and 60 cents, each with equal probability.
- The dividend for each **B-share** is consistently set at 24 cents more than the dividend of each corresponding **A-share**.

Specifically, at the end of each period, the dividend amount for each unit of A-shares and B-shares is determined as follows:

The dividend for each A-share is randomly drawn from 0, 8, 28, and 60 cents, each with equal probability.

The dividend for each B-share is consistently set at 24 cents more than the dividend of each corresponding A-share.

11 Shares and dividends (3)

That is to say, the dividend amount for each unit of **B-shares** is always 24 cents higher than that for each unit of **A-shares**.

For example:

- if each unit of **A-share** pays a dividend of 8 cents to the holder, then each unit of **B-share** will pay a dividend of $8 + 24 = 32$ cents to the holder.
- If each unit of **A-share** pays a dividend of 60 cents to the holder, then each unit of **B-share** will pay a dividend of $60 + 24 = 84$ cents to the holder.

That is to say, the dividend amount for each unit of B-shares is always 24 cents higher than that for each unit of A-shares.

For example, if each unit of A-share pays a dividend of 8 cents to the holder, then each unit of B-share will pay a dividend of $8 + 24 = 32$ cents to the holder.

If each unit of A-share pays a dividend of 60 cents to the holder, then each unit of B-share will pay a dividend of $60 + 24 = 84$ cents to the holder.

II Shares and dividends (4)

Attention:

(1) The **average dividend** per unit of **A-shares** each period is **24 cents**. This average is calculated from potential payouts of 0, 8, 28, and 60 cents, each paid with equal probability.

(2) Similarly, the **average dividend** per unit of **B-shares** each period is **48 cents**. This average is calculated from potential payouts of 24, 32, 52, and 84 cents, each paid with equal probability.

Please pay attention:

First, the average dividend per unit of A-shares each period is 24 cents. This average is calculated from potential payouts of 0, 8, 28, and 60 cents, each paid with equal probability.

Second, similarly, the average dividend per unit of B-shares each period is 48 cents. This average is calculated from potential payouts of 24, 32, 52, and 84 cents, each paid with equal probability.

II Shares and dividends (5)

The following table summarizes the minimum, average, and maximum total remaining dividends per share unit at the beginning of each period for each type of shares.

Period	Remain ning periods	X	The minimum , average , and maximum possible dividends paid per unit of A-shares per period			=	The total minimum , average , and maximum possible dividends for each unit of A-shares across all remaining periods			The possible dividend per unit of B-shares per period	The total minimum , average , and maximum possible dividends for each unit of B-shares across all remaining periods		
			0	24	60		0	240	600		24+A-share	240	480
1	10		0	24	60		0	240	600	24+A-share	240	480	840
2	9		0	24	60		0	216	540	24+A-share	216	432	756
3	8		0	24	60		0	192	480	24+A-share	192	384	672
4	7		0	24	60		0	168	420	24+A-share	168	336	588
5	6		0	24	60		0	144	360	24+A-share	144	288	504
6	5		0	24	60		0	120	300	24+A-share	120	240	420
7	4		0	24	60		0	96	240	24+A-share	96	192	336
8	3		0	24	60		0	72	180	24+A-share	72	144	252
9	2		0	24	60		0	48	120	24+A-share	48	96	168
0	1		0	24	60		0	24	60	24+A-share	24	48	84
end	0		–	–	–		0	0	0	–	0	0	0

The following table summarizes the minimum, average, and maximum total remaining dividends per share unit at the beginning of each period for each type of shares.

The second column records the number of remaining dividend payments.

The fourth, fifth, and sixth columns record the minimum, average, and maximum dividends per unit for A-shares.

Columns eight, nine, and ten record the total minimum, average, and maximum possible dividends per unit of A-shares for all remaining periods.

The subsequent columns contain similar information for B-shares.

II Shares and dividends (5)

The following table summarizes the minimum, average, and maximum total remaining dividends per share unit at the beginning of each period for each type of shares.

Period	Remain ing periods	×	The minimum , average , and maximum possible dividends paid per unit of A-shares per period			=	The total minimum , average , and maximum possible dividends for each unit of A-shares across all remaining periods			The possible dividend per unit of B-shares per period	The total minimum , average , and maximum possible dividends for each unit of B-shares across all remaining periods		
1	10		0	24	60		0	240	600	24+A-share	240	480	840
2	9		0	24	60		0	216	540	24+A-share	216	432	756
3	8		0	24	60		0	192	480	24+A-share	192	384	672
4	7		0	24	60		0	168	420	24+A-share	168	336	588
5	6		0	24	60		0	144	360	24+A-share	144	288	504
6	5		0	24	60		0	120	300	24+A-share	120	240	420
7	4		0	24	60		0	96	240	24+A-share	96	192	336
8	3		0	24	60		0	72	180	24+A-share	72	144	252
9	2		0	24	60		0	48	120	24+A-share	48	96	168
0	1		0	24	60		0	24	60	24+A-share	24	48	84
end	0		–	–	–		0	0	0	–	0	0	0

First, let us focus on the first row.

If you hold any type of shares from period 1 through period 10, those shares will pay dividends ten times.

Throughout the 10 periods, if the randomly selected dividends for each unit of A-shares are consistently 0 cents, the total dividends received from A-shares can be as low as zero cents, while those from B-shares can be as low as 240 cents.

Conversely, if the randomly selected dividends for each unit of A-shares are consistently 60 cents throughout the 10 periods, the total dividends received from A-shares can reach up to 600 cents, while those from B-shares can be as much as 840 cents.

II Shares and dividends (5)

The following table summarizes the minimum, average, and maximum total remaining dividends per share unit at the beginning of each period for each type of shares.

Period	Remain ing periods	×	The minimum , average , and maximum possible dividends paid per unit of A-shares per period			=	The total minimum , average , and maximum possible dividends for each unit of A-shares across all remaining periods			The possible dividend per unit of B-shares per period	The total minimum , average , and maximum possible dividends for each unit of B-shares across all remaining periods		
			0	24	60		0	240	600		24+A-share	240	480
1	10		0	24	60		0	240	600	24+A-share	240	480	840
2	9		0	24	60		0	216	540	24+A-share	216	432	756
3	8		0	24	60		0	192	480	24+A-share	192	384	672
4	7		0	24	60		0	168	420	24+A-share	168	336	588
5	6		0	24	60		0	144	360	24+A-share	144	288	504
6	5		0	24	60		0	120	300	24+A-share	120	240	420
7	4		0	24	60		0	96	240	24+A-share	96	192	336
8	3		0	24	60		0	72	180	24+A-share	72	144	252
9	2		0	24	60		0	48	120	24+A-share	48	96	168
0	1		0	24	60		0	24	60	24+A-share	24	48	84
end	0		–	–	–		0	0	0	–	0	0	0

Next, let us focus on the second row.

If you hold a single unit of A-shares from the second to the tenth period, the average total dividends for the remaining periods will be 216 cents, with a range from a minimum of zero cents up to a maximum of 540 cents.

Since the dividend per unit of B-shares is always 24 cents higher than that of A-shares per period, an additional 216 cents must be added to these figures for B-shares over the nine periods.

II Shares and dividends (5)

The following table summarizes the minimum, average, and maximum total remaining dividends per share unit at the beginning of each period for each type of shares.

Period	Remain ning periods	×	The minimum , average , and maximum possible dividends paid per unit of A-shares per period			=	The total minimum , average , and maximum possible dividends for each unit of A-shares across all remaining periods			The possible dividend per unit of B-shares per period	The total minimum , average , and maximum possible dividends for each unit of B-shares across all remaining periods		
			0	24	60		0	240	600		24+A-share	240	480
1	10		0	24	60		0	240	600	24+A-share	240	480	840
2	9		0	24	60		0	216	540	24+A-share	216	432	756
3	8		0	24	60		0	192	480	24+A-share	192	384	672
4	7		0	24	60		0	168	420	24+A-share	168	336	588
5	6		0	24	60		0	144	360	24+A-share	144	288	504
6	5		0	24	60		0	120	300	24+A-share	120	240	420
7	4		0	24	60		0	96	240	24+A-share	96	192	336
8	3		0	24	60		0	72	180	24+A-share	72	144	252
9	2		0	24	60		0	48	120	24+A-share	48	96	168
0	1		0	24	60		0	24	60	24+A-share	24	48	84
end	0		–	–	–		0	0	0	–	0	0	0

Similarly, if you hold a single unit of A-shares for any n periods, the dividends paid will range from a minimum of zero cents to a maximum of $n \times 60$ cents. The average total dividends will be $n \times 24$ cents.

Furthermore, the average dividend per period for B-shares is consistently 24 cents higher than that for A-shares.

Now, please answer the comprehension quiz to see if you understand the contents so far correctly. If you have questions, please ask the experimenter.

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III Shares transactions (1)

During the trading period, you are able to buy or sell shares.

When purchasing shares, you may use your existing experimental currency, and should your balance reach 0 cents, you can **borrow up to 2400 cents** from the computer **without interest**.

Alternatively, when selling shares, in addition to selling the shares you own, you can **borrow up to 4 units each of A-shares** and **B-shares** (with a total of 8 units) from the computer for selling. However, if you borrow shares from the computer to sell, your holdings will become **negative**. In such cases, **dividends** resulting from these negative shares will also be **negative**, and **the corresponding amount will be deducted from your experimental currency balance**.

Section 3, Shares transactions

During the trading period, you are able to buy or sell shares.

When purchasing shares, you may use your existing experimental currency, and should your balance reach zero cents, you can borrow up to 2400 cents from the computer without interest.

Alternatively, when selling shares, in addition to selling the shares you own, you can borrow up to 4 units each of A-shares and B-shares, with a total of 8 units, from the computer for selling.

However, if you borrow shares from the computer to sell, your holdings will become negative. In such cases, dividends resulting from these negative shares will also be negative, and the corresponding amount will be deducted from your experimental currency balance.

III Shares transactions (2)

As depicted in the slide, when trading shares, the amount of experimental currency you possess and the number of each type of stock you hold are displayed at the top of the experimental screen.

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III Shares transactions (3)

During the trading period, you are able to take the following actions:

- (1) To sell a unit of shares, **place a sell order.**
- (2) To purchase a unit of shares, **place a buy order.**

During the trading period, you are able to take the following actions:

First, to sell a unit of shares, place a sell order.

Second, to purchase a unit of shares, place a buy order.

III Shares transactions (4)

If you **sell** a share:

1. Enter the amount of cents you are willing to accept in the input field below the “Post selling price” button, then click “Post selling price” to submit your offer.

Post selling price	Your actions	Your transection price	Post buying price
<input type="text"/>	Buying Selling		<input type="text"/>
Sell order			Buy order

If you sell a share, type in the amount of cents you are willing to accept for a unit of the share in the input field below the “Post selling price” button on the left.

III Shares transactions (4)

If you **sell** a share:

2. Enter the amount of cents you are willing to accept in the input field below the “Post selling price” button, then click “Post selling price” to submit your offer.

※Please be aware that once an order is placed, it cannot be cancelled, so proceed with caution.

	Your actions	Your transection price	
Post selling price	Buying Selling		Post buying price
<input type="text"/>			<input type="text"/>
Sell order			Buy order
<input type="text"/>			<input type="text"/>

Then, clicking the “Post selling price” button will submit an order at the selling price you have entered.

Please note that once an order is placed incorrectly, it cannot be cancelled.

III Shares transactions (4)

If you **sell** a share:

3. Consequently, an order will be placed at the selling price you have entered.
(※Display order at the top with lower selling prices, visible to all participants within the same group.)

Sell orders placed will be displayed in the “Sell Order” box on the computer screen.

Within the box, orders with lower selling prices are displayed towards the top, ensuring visibility of all participants from the same group.

III Shares transactions (4)

If you **sell** a share:

4. If your submitted selling order is equal to or below the current highest buying price displayed in the “Buy Order” box, a transaction will be executed.

※ The transaction price will be equal to the highest buying price displayed on the screen.

If your submitted selling order is equal to or below the current highest buying price displayed in the “Buy Order” box, a transaction will be executed.

In this case, the transaction price will be equal to the highest buying price displayed on the screen.

III Shares transactions (5)

attention:

- (1) You can sell only one share per selling order, but as long as the trading period continues, you can continue to place new orders.
- (2) Furthermore, if your sell order is executed, all your existing sell orders for both types of shares **will be canceled** at the point of transaction. To sell an additional share, you must place a new sell order.

When placing a buy order, please pay attention to the following two points:
First, You can sell only one share per selling order, but as long as the trading period continues, you can continue to place new orders.
Second, if your sell order is executed, all your existing sell orders for both types of shares will be canceled at the point of transaction. To sell an additional share, you must place a new sell order.

III Shares transactions (6)

If you **buy** a share:

1. Enter the amount of cents you are willing to pay in the input field below the “Post buying price” button, then click “Post buying price” to submit your offer.

	Your actions	Your transaction price	
Post selling price	Buying Selling		Post buying price
<input type="text"/>			<input type="text"/>
Sell order			Buy order
<input type="text"/>			<input type="text"/>

If you buy a share, type in the amount of cents you are willing to pay for a unit of the share in the input field below the “Post buying price” button on the right.

III Shares transactions (6)

If you **buy** a share:

2. Enter the amount of cents you are willing to pay in the input field below the “Post buying price” button, then click “Post buying price” to submit your offer.
※ Please be aware that once an order is placed, it cannot be cancelled, so proceed with caution.

Post selling price	Your actions	Your transaction price	Post buying price
<input type="text"/>	Buying Selling	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Sell order			Buy order
<input type="text"/>		<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

Then, clicking the “Post buying price” button will submit an order at the buying price you have entered.
Please note that once an order is placed incorrectly, it cannot be cancelled.

III Shares transactions (6)

If you **buy** a share:

3. Consequently, an order will be placed at the buying price you have entered.

(※Display order at the top with higher buying prices, visible to all participants within the same group.)

Buy orders placed will be displayed in the “buy Order” box on the computer screen.

Within the box, orders with higher buying prices are displayed towards the top, ensuring visibility of all participants from the same group.

III Shares transactions (6)

If you **buy** a share:

4. If your submitted buying order is equal to or exceeds the current lowest selling price displayed in the “sell Order” box, a transaction will be executed.

※ The transaction price will be equal to the lowest selling price displayed on the screen.

Post selling price	Your actions	Your transaction price	Post buying price
	Buying Selling		
Sell order			Buy order

If your submitted buying order is equal to or exceeds the current lowest selling price displayed in the “Sell Order” box, a transaction will be executed.

In this case, the transaction price will be equal to the lowest selling price displayed on the screen.

III Shares transactions (7)

Attention:

1. You can buy only one share per buying order, but as long as the trading period continues, you can continue to place new orders.
2. If your buy order is executed, all your existing buy orders for both types of shares **will be canceled** at the point of transaction. To buy an additional share, you must place a new buy order.
3. For both sell and buy orders, if multiple orders exist at the existing lowest sell price or the existing highest buy price, **the transaction will be executed based on the order that was submitted earliest.**

When placing a buy order, please pay attention to the following three points:
First, you can buy only one share per buying order, but as long as the trading period continues, you can continue to place new orders.

Second, if your buy order is executed, all your existing buy orders for both types of shares will be canceled at the point of transaction. To buy an additional share, you must place a new buy order.

Third, for both sell and buy orders, if multiple orders exist at the existing lowest sell price or the existing highest buy price, the transaction will be executed based on the order that was submitted earliest.

III Shares transactions (8)

In the box labeled “Your transaction Price,” the **prices of your successful transactions** will be listed.

Post selling price	Your actions	Your transaction price	Post buying price
	Buying Selling		
Sell order			Buy order

For successful transactions, the prices of your successful transactions will be listed in the box labeled “Your Transaction Price.”

III Shares transactions (8)

For each type of shares, the box labeled "Your actions" will indicate whether you were **the buyer** or **the seller** in the transaction.

Post selling price	Your actions	Your transaction price	Post buying price
	Buying Selling		
Sell order			Buy order

For each type of shares, the box labeled "Your actions" will indicate whether you were the buyer or the seller in the transaction.

III Shares transactions (8)

In the center of the screen, all transaction prices concluded within your group for this period will be displayed.

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Now, let's practice trading by actually using the software. If you have any questions, please ask the experimenter.

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IV Information (1)

During each trading period, the experimental interface displays the total expected dividend value and the realizable dividends for each type of shares for the remaining periods.

Section 4, information.

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IV Information (1)

Clicking the “Historical Information” button at the bottom of the screen displays the number of shares bought and sold, the number held, the realized dividends, the total dividends for each type of shares, and the experimental currency balance in previous periods during that round.

The screenshot displays the game interface for "Round 1 period 3". At the top right, it shows "Remaining time [sec]: 1: 20". The main area is divided into sections for "A-share" and "B-share".

A-share section:

- Your holding: [Slider]
- The experimental currency (cent) you hold: [Slider]
- Expected total of undistributed dividends: [Slider]
- The realized value of dividends is equally probable to be 60, 28, 8, or 0 cents.
- The transaction prices of A-shares: [Slider]
- The transaction prices of B-shares: [Slider]

B-share section:

- Your holding: [Slider]
- Expected total of undistributed dividends: [Slider]
- The realized value of dividend is the realized dividend of A-share +24 cents

Historical Information "A" Table:

Units bought	Units sold	Units held	Realized dividends	Total dividends	Cents held	Periods
[Slider]	[Slider]	[Slider]	[Slider]	[Slider]	[Slider]	2
[Slider]	[Slider]	[Slider]	[Slider]	[Slider]	[Slider]	1

Historical Information "B" Table:

Units bought	Units sold	Unit held	Realized dividends	Total dividends	Cents held	Periods
[Slider]	[Slider]	[Slider]	[Slider]	[Slider]	[Slider]	2
[Slider]	[Slider]	[Slider]	[Slider]	[Slider]	[Slider]	1

Below the tables, it shows "The average transaction price of A-shares" and "The average transaction price of B-shares" with sliders.

Clicking the “Historical Information” button at the bottom of the screen displays the number of shares bought and sold, the number held, the realized dividends, the total dividends for each type of shares, and the experimental currency balance in previous periods during that round.

IV Information (1)

Clicking the “Historical Prices” button displays the **open, close, highest, lowest, and average prices**, as well as the **total trading volume** for **each type of shares** in your group **for each period of that round**.

Round 1 period 3

Remaining time [sec]: 1: 20

A-share Your holding: [] The experimental currency (cent) you hold: []

B-share Your holding: []

Expected total of undistributed dividends: []

The realized value of dividends is equally probable to be 60, 28, 8, or 0 cents.

The transaction prices of A-shares: [] The transaction prices of B-shares: []

Expected total of undistributed dividends: []

The realized value of dividend is the realized dividend of A-share +24 cents

Historical information "A"							Historical prices "A"						
Open prices	Close prices	Highest prices	Lowest prices	Average prices	Total trading volume	Periods	Open prices	Close prices	Highest prices	Lowest prices	Average prices	Total trading volume	Periods
[]	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]	2	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]	2
[]	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]	1	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]	1

The average transaction price of A-shares: []

The average transaction price of B-shares: []

Historical information "B"							Historical prices "B"						
Open prices	Close prices	Highest prices	Lowest prices	Average prices	Total trading volume	Periods	Open prices	Close prices	Highest prices	Lowest prices	Average prices	Total trading volume	Periods
[]	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]	2	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]	2
[]	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]	1	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]	1

Clicking the “Historical Prices” button displays the open, close, highest, lowest, and average prices, as well as the total trading volume for each type of shares in your group for each period of that round.

IV Information (1)

All information is displayed in reverse chronological order.

Round 1 period 3

Remaining time [sec]: 1: 20

A-share
Your holding

The experimental currency (cent) you hold

B-share
Your holding

Expected total of undistributed dividends
The realized value of dividends is equally probable to be 60, 28, 8, or 0 cents.

The transaction prices of A-shares.

The transaction prices of B-shares.

Expected total of undistributed dividends
The realized value of dividend is the realized dividend of A-share +24 cents

Historical information "A"

Open prices	Close prices	Highest prices	Lowest prices	Average prices	Total trading volume	Period
						2
						1

The average transaction price of A-shares

The average transaction price of B-shares

Historical information "B"

Open prices	Close prices	Highest prices	Lowest prices	Average prices	Total trading volume	Period
						2
						1

All information is displayed in reverse chronological order.

IV Information (2)

At the end of each period:

Round 1 period 3				Remaining time [sec]: 26
your trading results for this period.				
Your buying (A-shares)	Your selling (A-shares)	Your buying (B-shares)	Your selling (B-shares)	
				Experimental currency balance
				The realized dividend of A-share
				The realized dividend of B-share
				Number of A-shares held
				Number of B-shares held
				Total dividends you received this period
				New experimental currency balance
Your average buying price (A-share)				
Your average selling price (A-share)				
Your average buying price (B-share)				
Your average selling price (B-share)				
				OK

At the end of each period, the computer screen will display as follows.

IV Information (2)

At the end of each period:

- the left half of the screen displays a list of your buying and selling prices for each type of share upon successful transactions during the period

The left half of the screen displays a list of your buying and selling prices for each type of share upon successful transactions during the period,

IV Information (2)

At the end of each period:

Round 1 period 3 Remaining time [sec]: 26

your trading results for this period.

Your buying (A-shares)	Your selling (A-shares)	Your buying (B-shares)	Your selling (B-shares)
█	█	█	█

Experimental currency balance █
The realized dividend of A-share █
The realized dividend of B-share █
Number of A-shares held █
Number of B-shares held █
Total dividends you received this period █
New experimental currency balance █

Your average buying price (A-share) █
Your average selling price (A-share) █
Your average buying price (B-share) █
Your average selling price (B-share) █

OK

➤ the average buying price and average selling price

as well as the average buying price and average selling price.

IV Information (2)

At the end of each period:

Round 1 period 3

your trading results for this period.

Your buying (A-shares)	Your selling (A-shares)	Your buying (B-shares)	Your selling (B-shares)
█	█	█	█

Experimental currency balance	█
The realized dividend of A-share	█
The realized dividend of B-share	█
Number of A-shares held	█
Number of B-shares held	█
Total dividends you received this period	█
New experimental currency balance	█

Your average buying price (A-share)	█
Your average selling price (A-share)	█
Your average buying price (B-share)	█
Your average selling price (B-share)	█

OK

➤ The **experimental currency balance** at the start of the period, realized dividends for each type of shares during the period

The right half of the screen displays the experimental currency balance at the start of the period, realized dividends for each type of shares during the period,

IV Information (2)

At the end of each period:

Round 1 period 3
Remaining time [sec]: 26

your trading results for this period.

Your buying (A-shares)	Your selling (A-shares)	Your buying (B-shares)	Your selling (B-shares)
[Bar]	[Bar]	[Bar]	[Bar]

Your average buying price (A-share)	[Bar]
Your average selling price (A-share)	[Bar]
Your average buying price (B-share)	[Bar]
Your average selling price (B-share)	[Bar]

Experimental currency balance	[Bar]
The realized dividend of A-share	[Bar]
The realized dividend of B-share	[Bar]
Number of A-shares held	[Bar]
Number of B-shares held	[Bar]
Total dividends you received this period	[Bar]
New experimental currency balance	[Bar]

➤ **the number of each type of shares you hold, the total dividends received, and your experimental currency balance at the end of the period.**

the number of each type of shares you hold, the total dividends received, and your experimental currency balance at the end of the period.

V Endowment and payment (1)

- The experiment consists of **three rounds**, each comprising **10 trading periods**.
- Each trading period in the **first round lasts 180 seconds**, while in the **subsequent rounds**, each trading period is **90 seconds**.
- **At the start of each round**, all participants receive **1200 cents of experimental currency**; each **Type-A** participant receives **6 units A-shares**, and each **Type-B** participant receives **3 units B-shares**.
- If your holdings of each type of shares reduce to 0, you may borrow up to an additional **4 units A-shares** and **4 units B-shares**. However, this action will result in a negative share count, leading to negative dividends at the end of the period, which will be deducted from your experimental currency balance.
- You may borrow up to **2,400 cents** from the computer at **zero** interest.

Section 5, endowment and payment.

The experiment consists of three rounds, each comprising 10 trading periods. Each trading period in the first round lasts 180 seconds, while in the subsequent rounds, each trading period is 90 seconds.

At the start of each round, all participants receive 1200 cents of experimental currency.

In addition, each Type-A participant receives 6 units A-shares, and each Type-B participant receives 3 units B-shares.

If your holdings of each type of shares reduce to 0, you may borrow up to an additional 4 units A-shares and 4 units B-shares. However, this action will result in a negative share count, leading to negative dividends at the end of the period, which will be deducted from your experimental currency balance.

You may borrow up to 2,400 cents from the computer at zero interest.

V Endowment and payment (2)

- 100 cents = 50 Japanese Yen
- After the experiment ends, **the computer randomly selects one round.**
- The final payment you receive will be of an amount of the sum of **the payoff in Japanese Yen you earned in the round that the computer chose** plus the experimental participation fee of 1500 Yen. (rounded up to in units of 10 Yen)
- Please note that if the earned payoff in Japanese Yen is negative, it will be deducted from the participation fee.
- Your final payment will not lower than 1000 Japanese Yen even if the balance of experimental currency is **negative.**

At the end of each round, each 100 cents of experimental currency are converted to 50 Japanese yen.

After the experiment ends, the computer randomly selects one round.

The final payment you receive will be of an amount of the sum of the payoff in Japanese Yen you earned in that round plus the experimental participation fee of 1500 Yen. (rounded up to in units of 10 Yen)

Please note that if the earned payoff in Japanese Yen is negative, it will be deducted from the participation fee.

However, your final payment will not lower than 1000 Japanese Yen even if the balance of experimental currency is negative.

Now, please answer the comprehension quizzes to see if you understand the contents so far correctly. If you have questions, please ask the experimenter.

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